

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF CORRODED WEB-CORE SANDWICH PANEL STRIPES

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1 Introduction

The applications of steel sandwich panels in marine structures range from ship bulkheads, decks, hoistable ramps to superstructures. They offer weight and cost reduction compared to the traditional stiffened plate [1] due to the thin face plates located away from the neutral axis. One of the most prominent panel types is the web-core, where the orthogonal plates are periodic in transverse direction and joined by laser welding; see Fig. 1. However, their broad application in the maritime environment is, besides other factors, limited by the concern that corrosion may affect the thin plates and thereby reduce the strength of the panels unfavorably. This is especially crucial if sea water enters the panel and all four steel sandwich panel surfaces are exposed and subjected to corrosion.

The plate thickness reduction and surface profile characterization for sea corroding plates has been presented by Melchers et al. [2], while on the other hand Almusallam et al. [3] and Domzalicki et al. [4] showed that mechanical properties can be affected as well. Thus the overall collapse the structure is a function of the geometrical and material strength changes. Furthermore, many authors have investigated the ultimate strength of steel sandwich panels. Kolsters [5] and Romanoff [6] investigated the local ultimate strength of plate members of the sandwich panel under in-plane and out-of-plane loading. Kozak [7] studied the buckling strength of steel sandwich columns using experimental and numerical methods. This investigation was extended theoretically for buckling of plates, where the importance of laser-weld rotation stiffness was clearly demonstrated; see Jelovica et al. [8]. However, these investigations have been carried out on uncorroded specimens where the plate and weld thickness reduction has not been considered.

Therefore, experiments have been carried out in the EU Sandwich project [9] and DNV's investigation [10] on corroding steel sandwich panels, however, the exposure time was insufficient to affect the strength properties [9] or the strength was not tested at all [10]. Hence, there is a need to investigate the influence of the sea water exposure on the strength characteristics.

Therefore, this paper presents a series of ultimate strength tests on corroded web-core steel panels in three-point bending. The corrosion was achieved by submerging the specimens in the Baltic Sea for duration of one and two years. Furthermore, different types of corrosion prevention measures are used, including a core filling with polyurethane (PU) foam. Additionally, panels without corrosion were tested for comparison. As a result, the influence of corrosion on the panel stripe ultimate strength will be presented.

2 Experimental Investigations

2.1 General

Three sets of sandwich panel stripes are tested in three-point bending: four uncorroded specimens and five specimens submerged in water for one and two years, respectively. To investigate the influence of painted surfaces on the strength, unprotected specimens are tested for comparison. Furthermore, the core of the certain specimens is protected with corrosion inhibitor, applied either directly on the steel surface or mixed with a PU foam. The PU foam acts as additional core filling material. The specimen nomenclature and a short description are presented in Table 1.

2.2 Sea Water Corrosion Tests

The specimens were submerged in the Baltic Sea for one and two years. The test location was Isosaari

Marine Corrosion Station off Helsinki. The sea water is low-salinity brackish water. They were placed 2 meters below the sea level on a wooden rack positioned vertically to maximize the water flow around and inside the specimens due to wave motions.

2.3 Geometrical and Material Properties of the Specimens

The nominal thickness of the face plates is 2.5 mm and 4 mm for the web plates. The thicker web-plates are a result of laser-welding requirements. The length of the specimens is 1000 mm and the core height 40 mm. The total width of the panel is selected to be 300 mm, thus following beam theory in bending. The cross-section of the web-core sandwich beam is shown in Fig. 1. The core of some of the specimens is filled with PU foam Edulan C-1746.2 with a density, ρ , of about 40 kg/m³ and an elastic modulus in the direction of the web plates of $E_x = 8$ MPa. The surfaces were coated with Tikkurila Temacoat RM40 paint and/or protected with the Cortec VpCI-645 corrosion inhibitor mixed in the foam or Cortec VpCI-357 applied directly to metal surfaces.

Fig. 1. The cross-section of the web-core sandwich panel

Table 1. The nomenclature of the specimens

	Name	Exterior condition	Interior condition
No corrosion	0We1	No prot.	No protection
	0We2	No prot.	No protection
	0Wf1	No prot.	Foam
	0Wf2	No prot.	Foam
One-year corrosion	1We1	No prot.	No protection
	1We2	Paint	Paint
	1Wf1	Paint	Foam
	1Wf2	Paint	Inhibitor mixed with foam
	1Wf3	Paint	Inhibitor on surfaces only and filled with foam
year	2We1	No prot.	No protection
	2We2	Paint	Paint

2Wf1	Paint	Foam
2Wf2	Paint	Inhibitor mixed with foam
2Wf3	Paint	Inhibitor on surfaces only and filled with foam

The actual thickness of the plates is measured on the dog-bone specimens that were cut from the unprotected sandwich panels after the ultimate strength experiments. The average thicknesses presented in Table 2 are based on 30 and 200 measurements for the uncorroded and corroded specimens, respectively. Dog-bone specimens were cut along the length of the panel, from $x = 50$ mm to $x = 250$ mm. Numerical analysis unveiled that at this locations the material is stressed below the yield stress. Example of the stress-strain curves for the different plates is presented in Fig. 2.

The average thickness of all specimens is considered to be accurate since multiple measurements of the same point revealed a difference of up to 5 μ m only.

Table 2. The averaged measured thicknesses of the unprotected panels [mm]

Corrosion	t_t	t_{w1}	t_{w2}	t_{w3}	t_b
0 years	2.494	3.954	3.975	3.951	2.480
1 years	2.337	3.665	3.750	3.670	2.327
2 years	2.120	3.566	3.557	3.516	2.232

Fig. 2. Example of the stress-strain curves

2.4 Experimental set-up and test procedure

The instrumentation included displacement controlled force transducer HBM U2B with capacity of 100 kN and three displacement sensors HBM WA

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with maximum measuring range of 50 mm, located at $x=320$ mm, $x=466$ mm and $x=618$ mm. The test setup is shown in Fig. 3.

The displacement was adjusted manually in steps, recording the corresponding values of the displacements and the force. The loading procedure was as follows: initially, two loading cycles were made to reduce the residual stresses caused by production and handling. The material was stressed well within the elastic range since the maximum force used for this initial loading was 8 kN and the numerical simulations predicted the ultimate strength to be at about 50 kN. The experiment was then continued until the deflection of the bottom face plate, measured with the central displacement sensor, reached 40 mm. Afterwards, the sandwich panel was unloaded, followed by the final loading cycle to the same maximum deflection.

Fig. 3. The position of the specimen on the supports

3 Results and discussion

Force versus displacement at the central sensor of the tested specimens is presented in Figs. 4-9. The ultimate strength of the two uncorroded web-core panels is at 60 kN; see Fig. 4. The value decreases to 52 kN (13% reduction) and 50 kN (17%) for the one- and two-years corroded specimens, respectively. The reduction in strength follows the reduction in plate thickness, which is for the face plates 6.2% and 12.5% compared to the uncorroded panel. The average thickness reduction per exposed surface is linear in time for the face plates, 0.08 mm per year. In case of web plates, it slows down from 0.13 mm after the first year to 0.08 mm after the second year. The slower thinning can be explained by formation of corrosion product layer on the steel surfaces. Furthermore, the uncorroded specimens had 5% increase of the ultimate strength when filled with foam; see Fig. 5. However, the response

approaches the unfilled specimens once the foam fails. On the other hand, corrosion did not have any significant effect on the unfilled painted specimens as the ultimate strength remained at 60 kN; see Figs. 6 and 8. In combination with the inhibitor, the foam also provided a good protection from corrosion since all the filled specimens reached 58 kN; see Figs. 6-9.

Fig. 4. Force-displacement curves for the unprotected specimens

Fig. 5. Force-displacement curves for the foam-filled uncorroded specimens (i: inside the specimens)

Fig. 6. Force-displacement curves for the one-year corroded specimens – part 1 (i: inside, o: outside)

Fig. 9. Force-displacement curves for the two-year corroded specimens – part 2 (i: inside, o: outside)

Fig. 7. Force-displacement curves for the one-year corroded specimens – part 2 (i: inside, o: outside)

Fig. 8. Force-displacement curves for the two-year corroded specimens – part 1 (i: inside, o: outside)

Visual inspection of the panel's core unveiled foam degradation for the two-year corroded specimens 2Wf2 and 2Wf3 (Fig. 10b and 10c). In the former the foam is mixed with corrosion inhibitor. In the later, the inhibitor was applied on the steel surfaces and foam was put afterwards. On the other hand, the foam in specimen 2Wf1 (with no inhibitor) has good adhesion to steel surfaces and no voids (see Fig. 10a). Therefore, the inhibitors have negative influence on the foam inside the panel, leading to voids that can potentially be filled with water and cause corrosion. For the studied exposure time this was not observed in terms of strength, but it can be expected that with longer exposure period the steel surfaces inside the panel would be affected by corrosion.

Fig. 10. Panel's cross-section at $x=50$ mm for specimen a) 2Wf1, b) 2Wf2, c) 2Wf3

4 Summary

This paper described the results of the ultimate strength experiments on the web-core sandwich panel stripes. The panels were tested in three-point bending. Specimens were divided on three groups based on the extent of corrosion: (i) uncorroded, corroded for duration of (ii) one and (iii) two years. The experiments outlined the reduction in ultimate strength by 13% and 17% for the unprotected one- and two-years corroded web-core panels, respectively. Furthermore, the experiments showed that the corrosion protection via coating, filling the core with the foam and using the corrosion inhibitor is effective in restraining the corrosion for the studied time period. The use of inhibitor inside the core either mixed with the foam or applied to steel surfaces resulted in foam degradation and exposed the inner surfaces to sea water.

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